

Promoting Artificial Intelligence Through Skill Acquisition in Business Education Programme in Rivers State owned Universities.

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Abstract

This study was aimed at promoting Artificial Intelligence through skill acquisition in Business Education Programme in Rivers State Universities. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of this study consisted of 1,136 respondents which comprised of 35 Business Educators and 1101 Business Education students from the two universities in Rivers State. A sample size of 80 respondents was purposefully drawn from the universities. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were used for the study. Structured questionnaire was the instrument for data collection with four points scale. The instruments was face validated by two experts and the corrections and suggestions were affected by the researchers. The instrument was trial tested using 20 respondents from the department of Business Education, Niger Delta University Bayelsa State. The reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained with the use of Cranach Alpha formula. The researcher administered the 80 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents and retrieved complete copies. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The t-test statistics of no significant difference was used to test the null hypotheses. Based on the analysis the following findings were made; that Business Educators and Business Education students required most ICT and technical skills for promoting the use of Artificial Intelligence facilities (multimedia) in Business Education programme in Rivers State owned Universities. Based on the findings and conclusion the following recommendations are made among others; The government of Rivers State must enable to fund AI training Programme of personnel's in Rivers State University to help them acquire the necessary technical and ICT skills.

The universities management must ensure that AI facilities are adequately provided to the various departments, ensure regular power supply and network connection.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Business Education, Promoting, Skill Acquisition and Programme

Introduction

Business Education is a specialized phase of vocational education that prepares beneficiaries to enter teaching and office occupations as capable and intelligent members of the labour force. Business Education programme in Nigerian tertiary institution is offered under the following options. Office Management Technology, Management Education, Accounting Education and Marketing Education (Koko, 2018). Its primary objective is the acquisition of skills competencies for gainful employment in their professional areas. Amesi and Allison (2020), stated that Business Education Programme are type of educational programme that have to do with knowledge and skill which develops students physically, mentally and equip them to be self-dependent. Certain materials and equipment are needed to be provided in Business Education can only be used by qualified and experienced business educators. to achieve success, adequate number of lecturers are also needed to handle courses in business education programmes.

Business Education is seen as a discipline meant to prepare individuals economically, politically, socially and technologically and for transforming human resources and economic empowerment of people (Koko 2018). Human beings have greater and valuable roles to play in the process of economic development and growth. Consequently, the Business Education curriculum of institution needs to be prepared to meet up with the current challenges in practical skill acquisitions.

Business Education implies education for and about business. In recognition of the importance of business education to a country's growth and development, the Nigerian government introduced Business Education programme into the curriculum as contained in the National policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN 2013). In line with this, a number of colleges of education and universities also introduced business education into their programme. The importance of business education toward promoting artificial intelligence by the fact that it has become a choice subject in most colleges of education and in a number of universities – Federal, State and Private.

Skill acquisition is very vital in the life of every Nigerian Citizens. The reason why many Nigerian technicians earn more than some university graduates is because the technicians acquired more of skills when they were in their universities. Skills can take theories, the graduate were fed with when they were in their universities. Skill can take technicians to places they did not expect they would ever find themselves. Skill acquisition is the capacity to be trained on a proficient business occupation and become a proficient professional in it (Ernest, 2024). Efforts to improve the standard and quality of acquisition of practical skill inherent in business education courses to maximum level seems to be slowed down by a number of factors such as business education programmes, curriculum structures inadequate personnel, inadequate equipment and facilities for the teaching and learning of the skill, inadequate equipment materials for training and others (Jim, 2019), competencies can help in enhancing the application of artificial intelligence in Nigerian education system, particularly in higher institutions of learning.

Artificial intelligence has become the modern day strategy to capture the education system because of the potentials it can offer to enhance teaching and learning processes. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is technology that enables computer and machines to simulate human intelligence and problem-solving capacities.

According to Britanmica (2021), Artificial intelligence refers to computer systems that are capable of performing tasks traditionally associated with human intelligence. Among the types of Artificial intelligence are artificial general intelligence (AGI), Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI), Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI), Reactive Machine, limited Memory Theory of mind and self-ware. Artificial intelligence provide software that can reason on input and explain output. It can provide human like interactions with software and offer decision support for specific task, but it is not a replacement for human and would not be anytime soon. Artificial intelligence is beneficial in reading risk, ensuring automation bring efficiency and increase. Productivity in the operational system (Jim, 2023). Certain facilities such as computers and multi-media devices are utilized in Artificial intelligence system. (Michael, 2022).

Further, Business Education graduates do not possess the ICT skills and competencies to cope easily in the application of Artificial intelligence and utilization of its facilities in delivering most courses in Business education programme in Nigerian higher institutions of learning (Oyedele, 2000).

Statement of the Problem

Some universities in Nigeria still show poor level in providing artificial intelligence and applying artificial intelligence in the delivering of their programmes. Students who claimed to have been trained in computer skills during their course of study, generally still lacks the needed competencies to utilize and apply Artificial intelligence in daily activities. They could not perform as expected, establishing this empirically, was hence, the task of this study. The researchers upon this background intended to determine the strategies of promoting Artificial intelligence through skill acquisition in Business Education programme in Rivers State Universities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to determine strategies for promoting Artificial intelligence through skill acquisition in Business Education programme in Rivers State owned Universities. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the required skills in Business Education Programme for promoting Artificial Intelligence in Rivers State Universities.
2. Determine the impediments to skill Acquisition among Business Education students in promoting Artificial Intelligence in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study;

1. What are the required skills in Business Education for promoting Artificial Intelligence in Rivers State Universities?
2. What are impediments to skill acquisition among Business Education students in promoting Artificial Intelligence in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁: There is no significance in the response between the Business educators and students of Business Education in the required skills in promoting Artificial Intelligence in Rivers State Universities.
- Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the response of the Business Educators and students of Business Education on the impediment to skill acquisition for promoting Artificial Intelligence in Rivers State Universities.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of this study consisted of 1,136 respondents which comprised of 35 Business Educators and 1101 Business Education students from the two universities in Rivers State. A sample size of 80 respondents was purposefully drawn from the universities, (20 Business Educators and 60 business education students) learning skill related courses in year 3 from Rivers State university and Ignatius Ajuru university of Education for the purpose of the research. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were used for the study. Structured questionnaire was the instrument for data collection with four points scale of strongly agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (DA) and Strongly Disagreed (SDA). The instruments was face validated by two experts and the corrections and suggestions were affected by the researchers. The instrument was trial tested using 20 respondents from the department of Business Education, Niger Delta University Bayelsa State. The reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained with the use of Cranach Alpha formula. The researcher administered the 80 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents and retrieved complete copies. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The t-test statistics of no significant difference was used to test the null hypotheses. The t-calculated was compared with the table value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a given degree of freedom. The null hypothesis was not rejected where the calculated t-value was less than the t-table value with an appropriate degree of freedom; otherwise, the null hypothesis were rejected.

Results

Research question 1

What are the required skills in Business Education Programme. for promoting artificial intelligence integration in Rivers State University?

Table 1: Mean ratings on the required skills in Business Education Programme for promoting artificial intelligence in Rivers State University

S/N	Items relating to required skills include	X ¹	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	Remarks
1	ICT Skill	3.68	0.72	3.70	0.81	Agreed
2.	Technical/practical skill	3.55	0.68	3.88	0.72	Agreed
3.	Theoretical skill	3.70	0.65	3.75	0.68	Agreed
4.	Communication skills	2.92	0.58	3.40	0.59	Agreed
5.	Work attitude skills	3.81	0.53	3.40	0.59	Agreed
6.	Accounting skills	3.04	0.50	3.11	0.54	Agreed
7.	Managerial skills	3.12	0.51	2.93	0.48	Agreed
8.	Marketing skills	2.83	0.63	3.00	0.61	Agreed
9.	Entrepreneur skills	3.15	0.52	2.93	0.53	Agreed
10.	Public relation skills	2.54	0.61	2.98	0.60	Agreed
	Grand mean	3.23		3.25		Agreed

Keys: X₁ = mean response of Business Educators, SD₁ = Standard deviation of Business Educators, X₂ = means response of Business Education students, SD₂= Standard deviation of Business Education students.

Results in Table 1 revealed that, all the respondent strongly agreed to all items relating to required skills in Business Education programmes with a grand mean value of 3.23 and 3.25 for the two groups of respondents. This indicated that all skills stated are required by Business Educators and students in Business Education programme for promoting Artificial intelligence in Rivers State Universities. The standard deviation ranging from 0.50 to 0.61, means closeness of opinions.

Hypotheses 1: There is significant difference in the responses of Business Educators and Business Education students on the required skills in Business Education programme for promoting artificial intelligence in Rivers State Universities.

Table 2: t-test comparism of the opinions of Business Educators and Business Education students on the required skills in Business Education Programme.

Group	X	Sd	N	df	SE	t-cal	t-table	Remarks
Business Educators	3.23	0.56	20	78	0.08	0.90	1.96	Not rejected
Students	3.25	0.53	60					

The results in Table 2 shows that, t-calculated value of 0.90 is less than the t-table value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis indicate that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Business Educators and students on the required skills Business Education programme for promoting the integration of artificial intelligence in Rivers State Universities, hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Research Question 2: What are the impediments to skills acquisition among Business Educators for promoting artificial intelligence in Rivers State Universities?

Table 3: Mean ratings of respondents on the impediments to skill acquisition among Business Educators for promoting artificial intelligence in Rivers State University.

S/N	Items relating to impediments includes;	X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	Remarks
1.	Some business educators are not proficient in computer operation	3.28	0.71	3.89	0.480	Agreed
2.	Lack of fund	3.00	0.68	3.74	0.59	Agreed
3.	Lack of internet facility	2.80	0.92	3.97	0.52	Agreed
4.	Lack of AI machines	3.33	0.58	3.05	0.50	Agreed
5.	Lack of read-made AI software	3.68	0.62	3.12	0.51	Agreed
6.	Lack of technician personnel	3.70	0.73	3.42	0.60	Agreed
7.	Poor electricity supply	2.82	0.80	3.69	0.58	Agreed
8.	Poor network services	2.92	0.54	3.42	0.52	Agreed
9.	Poor application of teaching method with the facilities	3.66	0.50	3.36	0.59	Agreed
		3.91		3.51	0.54	Agreed

Results in Table 3, revealed that all the respondents agreed to all the items relating to the impediments to skill acquisition among Business Educators for promoting artificial intelligence in Rivers State University. The grand mean of 3.91 and 3.51 shows that certain impediments affected the integration of artificial intelligence in Business education programme in Rivers State universities. The standard deviation values ranging from 0.86 to 0.75 shows supported opinions.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the responses of Business educators and students on the impediments to skill acquisition in Business education programme for promoting artificial intelligence in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4: t-test comparism of the opinions of Business Educators s and students on the impediment to skill acquisition for business education programme for promoting AI.

Group	X	SD	N	Df	S/E	t-cal	t-crit	Remark
Business Educator	3.91	0.67	20	78	0.07	0.87	1.96	Not rejected
Students	3.51	0.54	60					

Results in table 4 shows that t-calculated value of 0.87 is less than t-table value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is included there no significant difference in the mean ratings Business Educators and students on the impediments to skill acquisition in Business Education programme for promoting AI in Rivers State Universities. Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Discussion of findings

Discussion of findings of the study is in accordance with research questions raised for this study. Findings from research one revealed that all respondents strongly agreed with the required skills in Business Education programme for promoting AI system. The hypothesis one tested

indicated there is no significant differences between Business Educators and students on the required skills in Business Education programme for promoting AI in Rivers State Universities. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Michael (2022) that stated the necessary skills are needed by students to enhance AI in our educational programme. The researcher are of the view that for promoting AI in our educational programme proficient ICT Skills are required by Business Educators and students. Programme Proficient ICT skill is required by both Business Educators and students.

The findings from research question two revealed that, all the respondents agreed to the impediments to skill acquisition among Business Educators and students for promoting artificial intelligence in Rivers State university. The finding of this was in agreement with Igwe (2015) that shows that certain challenges such as lack of ready-made software hindered the utilization of AI facilities in most Nigerian education programmes. Null hypothesis two tested revealed that there is no significant differences in the mean ratings of Business Educators and students on the impediments to skill acquisition for promoting AI in Business Education Programme in Rivers State Universities. The researchers are with the opinion that for effective application of AI, certain difficulties were encountered such as lack of technical personnel and shortage of AI facilities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that Business Educators and Business Educations students needed most ICT skills for promoting the use of Artificial Intelligence facilities in Business Education Programme in Rivers State Universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study and conclusion, the following recommendation were made;

1. The government of Rivers State must enable to fund AI training Programme of personnel's in Rivers State Universities to help them acquire the necessary technical and ICT skills.
2. The university management must ensure that AI facilities are adequately provided to the various departments, ensure regular power supply and network connection.

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